

Analysis protocol

Project title: Determination of the optimum strategy for interpretation of peak expiratory flow in the context of screening for impaired lung function

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Introduction

Spirometry is the gold standard for diagnosis of airway obstruction, but is often unavailable in low-income settings.¹ Measurement of peak expiratory flow (PEF) using inexpensive peak flow meters is sometimes recommended as an alternative to spirometry when the latter is not available.² However, the optimum strategy for interpretation of PEF results are not known. Should one use cutoffs based on absolute values of PEF, PEF in % predicted, PEF z-score, PEF/height², or gender-specific cutoffs based on absolute values of PEF?

Purpose

To determine how PEF readings should be interpreted to obtain the highest predictive value for impaired lung function (with spirometry as the gold standard).

Methods

Data source

Individuals aged ≥ 40 years from the NHANES 2007-2012 surveys (<https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/nhanes/index.htm>) who completed spirometry of acceptable quality. Only individuals with Non-Hispanic White, Non-Hispanic Black, and Mexican American ethnicities will be included, since the NHANES III equations (see below) only cover these ethnicities.

Data pre-processing

PEF values in the NHANES data were measured using spirometers and not peak flow meters. To emulate the imprecision of an EU scale Mini-Wright peak flow meter, the PEF values will be rounded off in the following manner:

- 1) PEF < 700 L/min will be replaced with the nearest multiple of 10 L/min
- 2) PEF > 700 L/min will be replaced with the nearest multiple of 20 L/min
- 3) PEF < 60 L/min will be replaced with 0 L/min
- 4) PEF > 880 L/min will be replaced with 880 L/min

Predicted values and z-scores for FEV₁, FVC and FEV₁/FVC will be calculated using the GLI 2012 equations.³ Since the GLI 2012 equations do not include equations for PEF, predicted values and z-score for PEF will be calculated using the NHANES III equations.⁴

Analyses

For each of the measures PEF, PEF in % predicted, PEF z-score, PEF/height², we will calculate the AUC (area under the receiver operating curve) for the detection of impaired lung function (defined as FEV₁ z-score < -1.645), and the difference in AUC between the different measures. 95% confidence intervals for the AUCs and the differences in AUCs will be calculated using a bootstrap procedure that accounts for the complex design of the NHANES surveys. Secondary and sensitivity analyses may use other outcomes; we will only analyze outcome with at least 20 cases. Table 1 provides an overview of the planned analyses, including secondary and sensitivity analyses.

Perspectives

Optimum interpretation of PEF has the potential to improve access to diagnostic services for pulmonary function impairment in low-income settings.

Publication of results

This protocol will be deposited on the open-access preprint server Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) along with the Stata syntax for conducting the analyses, before the analyses are carried out. The files will be put under an embargo and released no later than July 1, 2023. The results from the analyses will be summarized in a manuscript to be published as open access.

Ethics

The project is based on publicly available anonymous data. Under Danish legislation, no ethical review is necessary for such projects.⁵

References

- 1 Kibirige D, Sanya RE, Nantanda R, Worodria W, Kirenga B. Availability and affordability of medicines and diagnostic tests recommended for management of asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review. *Allergy Asthma Clin Immunol* 2019;15:14. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13223-019-0329-2>
- 2 Uganda Ministry of Health. Uganda clinical guidelines 2016. 2016. <http://library.health.go.ug/publications/guidelines/uganda-clinical-guidelines-2016>
- 3 Quanjer PH, Stanojevic S, Cole TJ et al. Multi-ethnic reference values for spirometry for the 3-95-yr age range: the global lung function 2012 equations. *Eur Respir J* 2012;40:1324-43. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1183/09031936.00080312>
- 4 Hankinson JL, Odencrantz JR, Fedan KB. Spirometric reference values from a sample of the general U.S. population. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 1999;159:179-87. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1164/ajrccm.159.1.9712108>
- 5 National Committee on Health Research Ethics. What to notify? <http://en.nvk.dk/how-to-notify/what-to-notify>, accessed 2020-01-01.

Table 1: Overview of analyses

Analysis number	Type of analysis	Binary condition to be predicted	Predictors	Participants	Complete or partial procedure	FVC and FEV1 quality attributes	Effort quality attribute	Comment
1	Primary	FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Complete	A or B	A	The outcome to be predicted is different degrees of FEV ₁ impairment.
2	Secondary	FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Separate analysis for males and females	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 1, but separate analysis by gender. This is because some authors have used gender-specific cutoffs when predicting obstruction using absolute values of PEF. This analysis will show how Z-scores and % predicted performs compared to the sex-specific cutoffs of absolute PEF.
3	Secondary	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN with FEV ₁ Z-score < -1.645, < -2, < -2.5, < -3 or < -4	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Complete	A or B	A	The outcome to be predicted is different degrees of airway obstruction (not just FEV ₁ impairment as in analysis 1).
4	Secondary	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Participants with FEV ₁ z-score < -1.645	Complete	A or B	A	This analysis is limited to participants with FEV ₁ impairment, and the outcome to be predicted is obstruction. It is expected that the performance of the model will be poor.
5	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ < LLN	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Separate analysis for each round of NHANES	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 1. In addition to the ROC plots, the sensitivity and specificity at each cutpoint will be compared between the three rounds.

6	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ < LLN	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Separate analysis for each of the three ethnicities	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 1. In addition to the ROC plots, the sensitivity and specificity at each cutpoint will be compared between the three ethnicities.
7	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ < LLN	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Complete or partial	A, B or C	A or C	As analysis 1, but with looser quality criteria for the spirometry.
8	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ % < 70, 60, 50, 35	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 1, but using FEV ₁ % to define the degrees of FEV ₁ impairment.
9	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ /FVC < LLN with FEV ₁ % < 70, 60, 50, 35	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 3, but using FEV ₁ % to define the degrees of airway obstruction
10	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ % < 80, 50 or 30	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Everyone	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 1, but using FEV ₁ % to define the degrees of FEV ₁ impairment (GOLD cutoffs)
11	Sensitivity	FEV ₁ /FVC < 0.7	PEF PEF% PEF Z-score	Participants with FEV ₁ % < 80	Complete	A or B	A	As analysis 4, but defining obstruction based on a fixed cutoff for FEV ₁ /FVC, and with impaired FEV ₁ defined as < 80% predicted.

For a description of the quality attributes, please refer to the documentation at https://wwwn.cdc.gov/Nchs/Nhanes/2011-2012/SPX_G.htm